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COMPARATIVE STUDY OF TEST SCORE PROCESSING SYSTEMS IN A UNIVERSITY SETTING

BY

¹DENIS, ACHUNG UYANAH & ²IDIKA, DELIGHT O.

¹DEPARTMENT OF CURRICULUM AND INSTRUCTIONAL TECHNOLOGY
CROSS RIVER UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY,
CALABAR, NIGERIA

²DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATIONAL FOUNDATIONS,
GUIDANCE AND COUNSELLING
UNIVERSITY OF CALABAR, NIGERIA

ABSTRACT

The issues arising from the exercise of combining scores are many and varied. One of them is the method that produces the best processed cumulative grade point average. To study the effect of method of processing on CGPA, four methods – cumulative percent grade point, percent grade point average, cumulative T-score grade point and T-score grade point average were applied on the test score of 50 year one students, obtained in their first and second semester of 2012/13 session. The scores were obtained from the department of mathematics CRUTECH, Calabar. The results of the two-way repeated measures ANOVA and the Friedman two-way ANOVA by ranks showed that there is a significant effect of method of processing on the CGPA. Based on these results, the cumulative T-score grade point system is recommended.

KEY WORD: Test Score Processing System, Cumulative Grade Point Average, Cumulative T-Score Average, Cumulative Percentage Average

INTRODUCTION

The issues arising from the exercise of combining examination scores have been exhaustively treated in the literature of educational testing practices. The use of percentages in award of grades is as old as educational testing itself. All these years, there have been developments in measurement that have studied that percentage scores used in awarding grades and subsequent combination of the grades to give a single composite score is wrong and misleading (Federal Ministry of Education, 1985). The Federal Ministry of Education (1985) specifically noted that fairness to all candidates in the same set of examinations can only be attained if all the scores are expressed on a common scale before the grading and grade combination exercise. Uyanah, Udoh and Joshua (1998) carried out a study on the effect of method of raw score transformation on the reported score. The raw scores were used as they are presently being used to obtain weighted mean scores. In the second method, the scores were transformed to T-scores at item level using group mean and standard deviation. Method three was the same with two except that the transformed scores were normalized. The fourth method was to transform the total raw score using group mean and standard deviation. The fifth method was still the transformation of the total raw score but using the standard normal distribution variable, Z. The results showed that normalized transformation whether at item level or total raw score level, produced the best comparable score ($\bar{x}$, = 50.02 and 50.46) for total score and item level transformation respectively. The raw score mean was the least (11.76). At the end, they recommended the application of normalized T-transformation. These results were only a confirmation of the hypothesised results in FME (1985) and Wood (1965).

Ogomaka and Osuala (2014) asserted that in Nigeria, and usually, university students' performances in a course examination are scored based on 100%, without regard to the fact that

- i. The number and structure of the items
- ii. Facility levels of the items and
- iii. The generosity or severity tendency of the scores is not the same. No effort, they continued, is made to remove/reduce the effect of any of these three factors. The obtained percentage scores of the students in each course examination are assigned grades and grade points based on a set of unjustified and unequal percentage intervals. As a result, they went on, two approximately equal scores 68% and 70% are treated unequally while 70% and 95% obviously unequal are treated equally. They argued that the unjustified variation in the treatment of examination scores is also introduced by (i) the use of tests of varying facility levels, (ii) unequal test lengths measured in terms of number of items and time allocation, (iii) scoring of responses to test items by scorers who have varying severity/generosity and (iv) the use of grades, grade points and the weighted grade point average. Today in Nigeria, almost all universities cumulate students' scores in terms of grade and grade points as directed by the National Universities Commission (NUC).

Ugomaka and Usuala (2014) carried out a study aimed at providing evidence that the students are not being treated equally, when

- i. percentage scores, weighted percentage average and cumulative weighted percentage average.
- ii. Grades, grade points, grade point averages and cumulative grade point average are used, and compared the results with when T-scores, weighted T-score average and cumulative weighted T-score average are used. Working with the results of 30 students in six courses, they showed that there is significant disparity in terminal grades assigned using percentages and those using grades and grade points. When they were compared with the T-score equivalent, the weighted T-score average, the use of T-score was superior.

This study (Ogomaka and Osuala, 2014) made great advancement in addressing this long-standing issue of test score statistics. The procedures advocated are not new. This would be a perfection of the practice of classical Test theory (CTT), which is being abandoned by many educational systems, for a high quality theory, the item response theory (IRT). Their observation that percentage and grade point computation of cumulative grades is less demanding, accounting for the popularity of percentage and grade point is true. However this is to the detriment of the students, as they observed that when a scoreless than 40% is discarded, the student losses them (scores) forever. The procedure they finally recommended is the used of weighted T-score average.

The only issue left hanging in this study (Ogomaka and Osuala, 2014) is the comparison of either their ranks under the three approach or the final grade point based on which the classification of degrees is done. One wonders therefore, what the results would look like if grading T-score is done at course level and when grading is done after the computation of weighted T-score. This will represent the final destination and one would like to know if the differences in the final grade point averages are significant. This is the gap that this paper seeks to address. The null hypotheses to be tested are:

- i. There is no significant difference in mean grade points due to method of obtaining the grade points.
- ii. There is no significant difference in the ranks of students' scores due to method of obtaining grade point average

Methodology

The population for that study consisted of all year one undergraduate students of Cross River University of Technology admitted in the 2012/2013 academic session. To reduce the between lecturers and between students variation, only those who offered the same and number of courses and were taught by the same set of lecturers were selected. By the time these requirements were met, there was need for application of any known sampling technique to meet inferential research

requirements. So fifty (50) students' results were randomly selected from the 128 students that met the requirement. A sample size of 50 (greater than 30) was considered large enough for inference purpose.

The obtained percentage scores of 50 students the entire department of Mathematics and Statistics for first and second semester year one were analysed.

Method I

The scores were processed using grade assigned by the different lecturers. The grade point average and CGPA were computed and their ranks assigned using the procedure approved by NUC (2013) and used by Ogomaka and Osulala (2014).

Method II

The percentage total scores were transformed to T-scores, using the procedure recommended by measurement experts (Ebel, 1979; Joshua, 2005 and Ogomaka & Usuala, 2014). The weighted T-score average and the cumulative weighted T-score averages were obtained. The cumulative weighted T-score were then graded and awarded grade points. Based on these final results, ranking was done.

Method III

The percentage score were transformed to T-scores and grades awarded to the T-score using the guide provided by

NUC: 70 and above – A	= 5 points
60 – 69 - B	= 4 points
50 – 59 – C	= 3 points
45 – 49 – D	= 2 points
40 – 44 - E	= 1 points
Below 40 – F	= no point

From this point, the normal procedure for computing grade point average and cumulative grade point average was followed. Based on the CGPA, the students were ranked.

Method IV

The percentage scores were weighted to produce weighted average and cumulative percentage average using the procedure applied by Ogomaka and Osuala (2014). Grade points were then awarded to the cumulative weighted percentage averages. Ranks were then assigned.

The obtained grade point averages were further analysed using two – way ANOVA for repeated measures design and the Friedman two – way ANOVA by ranks. F-ratio and Least Significance Difference tests were used with the parametric ANOVA to compare cumulative grade point averages. Friedman test statistic, defined as

$$X_r^2 = \frac{12}{nk(k+1)} \sum_{i=1}^k R_i^2 - 3n(k+1)$$

was used to compare the ranks, where

n = sample size = 50

k = number of treatments = 4

R_i = sum of the ranks in the treatment.

Results and Interpretations

The cumulative grade point average obtained from the four processing systems, for the 50 students are shown in table 1.

From Table 1, it can be seen that the CGPA obtained by cumulating the percentages is highest, followed by those obtained by combining grades that are based on percentage grouping. The least is that produced by combining grades that were based on T-scores. To test for the significance of the cumulative grade point average obtained using the four processing systems,

two-way ANOVA for repeated measures design was carried out. The descriptive statistics are given in Table 2.

Table 2: Two-way ANOVA of CGPA by processing method

Method	Mean	SD	Std Error
Percent CPPT	3.400	.881	.040
T-score CTSPT	2.360	1.005	.040
T-score (TS)	2.279	.770	.040
Percent CGPA %	3.280	.803	.040
Total	2.830	1.004	.020

Source	Sum of Sq	df	Mean sq	F	P
Corrected model	189.201	52	3.638	46.386*	.001
Intercept	160.457	1	1601.451	20416.5*	.000
Processing method	52.603	3	17.534	223.54*	.000
Person	136.598	49	2.788	35.54*	.002
Error	11.531	147	0.078		
Total	1802.188	200			
Corrected total	200.731	199			

Significant at 0.05, $p < 0.05$, $R^2 = 943$ adj. R – squared = .922

From Table 2, it can be observed that the highest mean CGPA was obtained from the cumulative percent method (3.400) while the least was obtained from the cumulative T-score method (2.360). When these mean CGPAs were tested for significance using F – ratio test, the p – value (.000) associated with the computed F – value (223.540) was found to be less than the chosen level of significance (0.05). The null hypothesis of no significant effect of the method of processing the test scores was rejected in favour of the alternative. This means that method of processing test score has a significant effect of the resulting CGPA.

To find out which pair of mean CGPA was responsible for the observed significant values, LSD test was applied. The results are given in Table 3.

Table 3: LSD multiple pairwise comparison of mean CGPA by processing method

Method	CPPT	CTSPT	CGPA (TS)	Percent CGPA
Percent CPPT	3.400	.040	.121	.120
T-score CTSPT	.000	2.360	.081	.920
T-score CGPA (TS)	.000	.150	2.279	1.001
Percent CGPA	.034	.000	.000	3.280

*significant at 0.05 level, $P < 0.05$.

* values above diagonal are mean differences and below are p-values and along the diagonal are treatment means

From Table 3, only the mean difference between the CGPA obtained using T-score GRPT and T-score CGPA was not significant. All others were significant.

To find out if these processing methods also produce significant ranking of the candidates on the basis of their CGPA, Friedman two way ANOVA by ranks was carried out. The results are given in Table 4.

From Table 4, and using the obtained values of R, the Friedman test statistic computed was 110.31 with an associated probability of 0.001. Since this associated probability is less than the chosen level of significance (.05), the null hypothesis was rejected in favour of the alternative. This means that the four processing methods produced significantly different ranking of the candidates with the cumulative percent, producing the highest rankings of 29 (58%) out of 50 candidates.

Table 1: Cumulative Grade Points by the Four Processing system

S/N	CPPT	CTSPT	CGPA(TS)	CGPA %
1	4	3	2.80	3.91
2	4	3	3.14	4.17
3	4	3	3.26	4.11
4	4	3	2.46	3.63
5	3	1	1.54	2.63
6	3	1	1.26	2.66
7	4	3	2.86	3.94
8	3	3	2.37	3.34
9	3	2	2.29	3.17
10	4	3	2.83	4.09
11	3	3	2.29	3.31
12	2	1	0.77	1.69
13	3	2	2.31	3.54
14	4	3	2.57	3.69
15	4	3	3.14	4.06
16	4	3	2.82	3.57
17	1	0	0.54	1.34
18	4	3	2.43	3.51
19	3	2	2.20	3.29
20	5	4	3.37	3.97
21	3	2	1.69	3.09
22	3	1	1.94	2.40
23	3	2	1.80	2.49
24	4	3	3.09	4.17
25	3	1	1.31	2.20
26	3	2	1.42	2.46
27	4	3	2.91	3.69
28	4	3	2.37	4.00
29	1	0	0.89	1.29
30	4	3	2.40	3.54
31	4	3	2.91	3.91
32	4	3	3.14	4.17
33	4	3	3.26	4.11
34	4	3	2.26	3.63
35	3	1	1.34	2.63
36	3	1	1.49	2.66
37	4	3	2.86	3.94
38	3	3	2.26	3.34
39	3	2	2.17	3.17
40	4	3	2.71	3.86
41	3	3	2.29	3.31
42	2	1	0.77	1.69
43	3	2	2.31	3.42
44	4	3	2.57	3.57
45	4	3	3.14	3.94
46	4	3	2.83	3.57
47	1	0	0.54	1.34
48	4	3	2.42	3.51
49	3	2	2.20	3.29
50	5	4	3.37	3.97

CPPT means Cumulative Percent Point, CTSPT means Cumulative T-Score Point, CGPA (TS) means Cumulative Grade Point Average based on T-scores and CGPA% means Cumulative Grade Point Average based on Percentages

Table 4: Cummulative Grade Point Average Ranks for Friedman Test

S/N	Percent GRPT	T-score RPT	T-score CGPA	Percent CGPA
1	4 (4)	3 (2)	2.80 (1)	3.91 (3)
2	4 (3)	3 (1)	3.14 (2)	4.17 (4)
3	4 (3)	3 (1)	3.26 (2)	4.11 (4)
4	4 (4)	3 (2)	2.46 (1)	3.63 (3)
5	3 (4)	1 (1)	1.54 (2)	2.63 (3)
6	3 (4)	1 (1)	1.26 (2)	2.66 (3)
7	4 (4)	3 (2)	2.86 (1)	3.94 (3)
8	3 (4)	3 (2)	2.37 (1)	3.34 (3)
9	3 (3)	2 (1)	2.29 (2)	3.17 (4)
10	4 (3)	3 (2)	2.83 (1)	4.09 (4)
11	3 (2.5)	3 (2.5)	2.29 (1)	3.31 (4)
12	2 (4)	1 (2)	0.77 (1)	1.69 (3)
13	3 (3)	2 (1)	2.31 (2)	3.54 (4)
14	4 (4)	3 (2)	2.57 (1)	3.69 (3)
15	4 (3)	3 (1)	3.14 (2)	4.06 (4)
16	4 (4)	3 (2)	2.82 (1)	3.57 (3)
17	1 (2)	0 (1)	.54 (3)	1.34 (4)
18	4 (4)	3 (2)	2.43 (1)	3.51 (3)
19	3 (3)	2 (1)	2.20 (2)	3.29 (4)
20	5 (4)	4 (3)	3.37 (1)	3.97 (2)
21	3 (3)	2 (2)	1.69 (1)	3.09 (4)
22	3 (4)	1 (1)	1.94 (2)	2.40 (3)
23	3 (4)	2 (2)	1.80 (1)	2.49 (3)
24	4 (3)	3 (1)	3.09 (2)	4.17 (4)
25	3 (4)	1 (1)	1.31 (2)	2.20 (3)
26	3 (4)	2 (2)	1.42 (1)	2.46 (3)
27	4 (4)	3 (2)	2.91 (1)	3.69 (3)
28	4 (3.5)	3 (2)	2.37 (1)	4.00 (3.5)
29	1 (3)	0 (1)	0.89 (2)	1.29 (4)
30	4 (4)	3 (2)	2.40 (1)	3.54 (3)
31	4 (4)	3 (2)	2.91 (1)	3.91 (3)
32	4 (3)	3 (1)	3.14 (2)	4.17 (4)
33	4 (3)	3 (1)	3.26 (2)	4.11 (4)
34	4 (4)	3 (2)	2.26 (1)	3.63 (3)
35	3 (4)	1 (1)	1.34 (2)	2.63 (3)
36	3 (4)	1 (1)	1.49 (2)	2.66 (3)
37	4 (4)	3 (2)	2.86 (1)	3.94 (3)
38	3 (2.5)	3 (2.5)	2.26 (1)	3.34 (4)
39	3 (3)	2 (1)	2.17 (2)	3.17 (4)
40	4 (4)	3 (2)	2.71 (1)	3.86 (3)
41	3 (2.5)	3 (2.5)	2.29 (1)	3.31 (4)
42	2 (4)	1 (2)	0.77 (1)	1.69 (3)
43	3 (3)	2 (1)	2.31 (2)	3.42 (4)
44	4 (4)	3 (2)	2.57 (1)	3.57 (3)
45	4 (4)	3 (1)	3.14 (2)	3.94 (3)
46	4 (4)	3 (2)	2.83 (1)	3.57 (3)
47	1 (3)	0 (1)	0.54 (2)	1.34 (4)
48	4 (4)	3 (2)	2.42 (1)	3.51 (3)
49	3 (3)	2 (1)	2.20 (2)	3.29 (4)
50	5 (4)	4 (3)	3.37 (1)	3.97 (2)
R	177	81.5	73	168.5

Discussion

The results of this study have strengthened the position of Ogomaka and Usuala (2014), that in terms of quantity of points, the weighted Percent Grade Point Average (CGPA%), gives the best results. So if one is interested in quantity, just the numerical value, then the current percent CGPA system practiced in all Nigerian universities should be dropped and CGPA%, adopted.

Of all the end products of the process, the products that are based on percent are higher in numerical value than those based on normalized T-scores. However, the presence of inequities in the use of weighted percent Average the entire test or examination being easy or very difficult and scorer unreliability, are great sources of concern. As long as these sources remain, one should have little faith in the beautiful grades. The weighted percent grade point average is worse, having four (4) sources of inequities – the two related to weighted percent average and additional two: the assignment of different grades or grade points to approximately equal scores and the assignment of same grade/grade point to scores that are clearly different (Ogomaka & Osuala, 2014). There is the fifth and sixth inequities – the scores less than 40 that are not credited to the student and the meaninglessness of the zero point awarded to a failure grade there from. The weighted percent average system overcomes these two inadequacies by making use of every score earned by the students. If one should recommend for practice, the weighted grade point average should be the first to be dropped.

The cumulative grades obtained based on T-scores are smaller in numerical values than their percent equivalents. However, in all literature on psychometry and educational tests and measurement, their quality have been attested to (Ogomaka, 2004; Joshua, 2004; Federal Ministry of Education, 1985; Wood, 1965; Ogomaka & Osuala, 2014) as being free of the four sources of inequities; producing performance indices that are comparable across persons and subjects or courses.

The CGPA obtained by cumulative T-score is better than that obtained by grading based on T-scores before computing the weighted grade point average. Part of the reason is that the cumulative T-score has the advantage of cumulative percent grading. Consequently, one is left with no other option than recommend for practice the cumulating T-score.

In this study the final grade was based on the current grading scheme issued by NUC. As long as one cannot rationalize the uneven intervals in the grading scheme, a revision is necessary.

Conclusion

From this study, one can conclude that the test score processing systems have a significant effect on CGPA with cumulative percent being best in terms of quantity and cumulative T-score being best in terms of quality. If we must go for quality in reported grades, then the best option is to cumulate T-scores.

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